

USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7595291>

Abstract

In the article, the author reveals how to achieve the effectiveness of the use of digital technologies in the educational process using the example of creating and using video lessons.

Keywords: digital technologies, digital educational technologies, video lesson, media, efficiency.

In our country important reforms are implementing to promote information and communication technologies. On the basis of these reforms, a number of tasks related to the training of mature specialists for the sphere have been defined. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-60 "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" on January 28, 2022, as well as, in order to implement the priority tasks of bringing the sphere of information and communication technologies to a new level, the task of establishing the education of more than 6.5 thousand young people in the sphere of information technologies per year through the development of personnel training activities in the sphere of digital technologies in the form of distance education was defined¹. In addition, given the quick changes in the worldwide scale, it will be vital to pay attention to the issue of the competitiveness of trained personnel. Such kind of drastic changes will force the world education system to quickly change and adapt. The transition to the digital age is taking place all over the world in all spheres, which is evident in the fact that tablets, mobile phones, smart watches, and virtual reality glasses have firmly entered the daily lives of today's students. The digital technologies are rapidly entering the education system. The use of presentations, videos and audio programs to improve the management and organization of education as well as the effectiveness of the educational process is no longer new. However, the use of new, effective and interesting methods of digital technologies is one of the key points of the 21st century education system. In this regard, pedagogues have a very responsible and arduous task, in which in the current conditions of information, it is necessary to be able to attract learners by forming the necessary educational content in the environment of digital technologies. And it requires a little more effort to accomplish this procedure with young people who grew up around digital technologies. Because it will be more difficult to interest them with simple traditional contents and opportunities. On the other hand, every contemporary teacher in the pedagogic personnel training system today is aware of the requirement to conduct instruction in a novel manner while utilizing innovative computer technology in the educational process. This requires for each pedagogue to put in continuous effort into himself,

to research and to create his own digital educational contents.

Digital educational contents are photos, video clips, models, animations, role-playing games, cartographic materials and necessary methodological recommendations, it is necessary for the organization of the educational process and is presented in a digital form "connected" with the planning of the lesson, selected according to the content of a certain textbook was provided. Digital educational contents (electronic textbooks, tutors, simulators, interactive kits, dictionaries, reference books) help the teacher to make the lesson interesting and the students learn the material successfully. Digital educational contents can be used at all levels of education as follows:

- explaining new material;
- strengthening;
- repeating;
- controlling of knowledge, skills and qualifications.

It makes it possible to expand and update the forms of using digital educational contents, activities of students in computer science and information technology lessons, activate attention and increase the creative potential of a person. The construction of diagrams, tables, presentations allows to save time and arrange the material more aesthetically. The use of crosswords, illustrations, drawings, puzzles, various exciting tasks, tests increases interest in the lesson, makes it more interesting. The computer science and information technology lessons require a special method. They should be bright, emotional, involving richly illustrated material and it will be used video accompaniment. All this can be provided by computer technology with multimedia capabilities. It can be used to explain new material, strengthen knowledge and perform creative tasks in computer science and information technology lessons. Your presentation can contain anything you want: drawing, diagrams, tests, videos and other link of digital educational contents. The presentation can be considered universal compared to other sources. For instance, animations and illustrations can be used to explain new material: demonstrates these contents clearly the learning material, allows observing various natural phenomena. These contents can also be used to organize work.

¹ <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/6166539> - O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022 yil 22 avgustdagi PQ-357-sonli "2022-2023 yillarda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari

sohasini yangi bosqichga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi qarori.

The choice of digital educational tools in the lesson is made depending on the purpose of the lesson. We have shown the views of digital educational contents

and the tasks of their practical application at different stages of the lesson in the following diagram (Picture No 1).

Picture № 1. The types of digital educational contents and their functions.

There are various types of digital technologies in education, it will provide the achievement of high efficiency, if used in their proper place in the organization and management of the educational process. For instance, video materials are the most interesting type of educational content presented in the educational process. The video lesson is a special type of organizing of the educational process, which consists in the use of various video equipment in the lessons: screen, projector, etc. The video lessons are becoming more and more popular due to their high efficiency.

What is video lessons? Video lessons are a video-based learning system. It is one of the most effective and convenient systems in today’s modern life. The

video lesson is a format of distance education, which involves the transmission of educational material through video recordings.

D.A. Gatovskaya noted that “watching a video lesson is much more interesting than sitting with a textbook and reading the text, so you can watch it at any time, even do things unrelated to the lesson” [1].

Scientists from Russian Federation Vyacheslav Yurchenkov and Yuliya Shustrova have been mentioned in their research based on analytical reports of ATD, Harvard Business Publishing Education, Digital Information World and Kaltura present the effectiveness of video as follows (Picture № 2):

Picture № 2. The effectiveness of video materials.

In particular, it offers a wider range of opportunities than other subjects, especially for use in Computer Science and Information Technology lessons. The clear example of this is the recording and use of computer screen sequences as video material. The sequence of actions that the student should learn is presented on the big screen. This requires the student to remember only the sequences and repeat them when necessary. At first

glance, it seems like a very easy and light process. However, this is just using ready-made video material. But the main problem for the teacher is that he must be able to create the video material first based on all the requirements. You need competent software and a computer that can run it in order to create. There are many and varied software tools for this. We recommend you

Wondershare Filmora. Learn more about the opportunities of program for producing video content.

After launching Filmora, left click on “New Project” to enter the editing interface and start a new project. Regardless of the options you select in “Getting Started”, the program opens an editing interface:

Media – this is where you will find all your media files, including: video clips, photos and music. In addition, it includes text, effects and many other contents that you can use in your projects. The selecting of clips in the media library: click the thumbnail of a single media file to select it. Click the first (initial) thumbnail to select a sequence of media files, press and hold the “Shift” key, then click the last thumbnail. Adding the videos and other media to your timeline:

Way 1. Click on the project thumbnail, then drag it onto the timeline with the mouse.

Way 2. Right click the desired media thumbnail and select one of the following options:

- Insert – adding media to the selected lane in the interface. Any media in the lane to the right of the inserted media moves to the right by the length of the inserted clip.

- Overwrite – add your media files to the selected lane in the playback area and replace all the effects available here.

- Add (add to the end) – add media as the last fragment of the selected lane.

- Add to new track – add newly created lane media with no other media.

Apply effects. The ability to attach filters and overlays further expands your creative possibilities. You can completely change the look of your video footage with just a few clicks. Wondershare Filmora allows you add as many effects and overlays as you want. There are three ways:

1. Click on the “Effects” button in the “Media Library” and then you can select the filters or overlays you like to add to your project.

2. Hover the cursor onto the thumbnail of the effect you want to use. When you see the “Plus” icon in the middle, click on it and the effect will be added to the timeline.

3. Place the **filter/overlay** directly on the video clip in the timeline using the mouse. Effects are applied to the entire video clip.

Filter Sorting. All filters and overlays are sorted into themed categories (i.e. Faux Film or Bokeh Blurs) to make them easy to find. Go to the “Effects” menu and see the categories on the left and start browsing. Wondershare Filmora enables you change the duration or opacity of filter effects:

- The default length is five seconds, but you can drag the edge of the effect in your timeline to change its duration.

- Alpha opacity (transparency) property can have a value of 0-100. A lower value makes the filter more transparent. Double click the filter on the timeline to customize its opacity.

- Right click on a filter effect in the Effects menu and select **Add to Favorite**. Then, go to the **Favorite** category to find it again quickly.

Elements. Elements are motion graphics that you can use to decorate your video. They can be inserted between your video clips to improve the video flow or increase the quality. Filmora includes more than 20 free sounds. To add an item to your project:

- Go to Elements and select the “Element” button you want to add to your project.

- Bring it to the timeline.

After you've open the “Transitions” effects menu, you can select the “Transition” effects you like and drag it to the timeline between 2 video clips. To apply a transition to a custom video clip or image:

- Drag a video clip or image to the timeline.

- Open the jump menu.

- Choose a transition type and drag it to the beginning or end of a video clip or image in the timeline.

To change the duration of a transition, double click it in the timeline, and then enter a new duration. You can also click and drag forward or backward to start or end a transition within a video clip or image.

Export video to computer. When complete the video editing, click “Export” and then select the “Local” tab in the “Export” window. Then select the export format. Filmora currently supports the following formats: WMV, MP4, AVI, MOV, F4V, MKV, TS, 3GP, MPEG-2, WEBM, GIF and MP3.

The digitization is becoming an integral element of the development of all aspects of society, including the education system. Digitalization in all aspects of technology and national economy at the time of rapid development of information technology, in the process of teaching in higher education institutions, regardless of their goals, there is a need to use a variety of interactive tools and online contents for direct and effective collaboration between existing teachers and students. In this regard, the correct selection of hardware and software for creating video lessons, the formation of educational contents, and the correct use of them will increase the motivation and effectiveness of the educational process.

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